

Using Methodology in Multimedia Resources in Teaching a Foreign Language

Author(s), RUSTAMOV ALIJON

Abstract:

The article reveals the need to use innovative technologies in foreign language classes. They have a number of advantages over other educational information technologies, as they allow: to improve the organic combination of traditional forms and methods of education with innovative ones: to implement a training information, game modeling design and analytical function.

Keywords: methodology, teaching, training, multimedia resources, foreign languages, teaching process,

EASIJ

Accepted 2 May 2021

Published 6 May 2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4740066

About Author

**Author(s):
RUSTAMOV ALIJON**

Teacher of Uzbek State world languages university,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

INTRODUCTION.

In the light of the new paradigm of education, the central problems of teaching a foreign language are the determination of the goals and content of education. The process of acquiring students of personal experience in communicating with a foreign language culture of situations of practical use of language as an instrument of intercultural knowledge of interaction. In this regard, the objective need to integrate information technologies into the educational process, allowing students to be involved in situations of intercultural communication, since today there is a global network. The Internet provides a wide range of opportunities for students to enter into authentic intercultural interaction with representatives of the language being studied.

MAIN PART.

Foreign language education cannot be imagined without the use of multimedia teaching tools. The possibility of a real communication process in English. The need to bring the educational environment closer to the real conditions of the functioning of the language and culture studied, of course, are relevant tasks of the methodology of teaching foreign languages. The most significant group of advantages lies in the methodological advantages of computer training.

For example, teachers use the ability of a computer to input information to create the simplest training programs in the form of exercises. The technical advantages of teaching English using multimedia are that sound cards allow the user to record their speech, and then listen and compare it with the pronunciation of native speakers.

Multimedia is an excellent means of interactive communication between different language groups, which is especially pronounced when using a computer network. It can be both a local network connecting several computers in the same educational institution, and the Internet - a global network connecting millions of users around the world. Thanks to the optimal combination of the capabilities of a number of technical means of training (lingaphone room, video films, television, radio. newspapers, magazines, books, bibliographic directories, telephone) and having additional capabilities (interactivity. graphic capabilities T e), multimedia provides almost limitless opportunities for teaching and self-learning Multimedia technology designed to contribute to the development of Individual educational trajectories to more adapt the content of educational material to the individual characteristics of students, their level of knowledge and skills. The use of modern technologies by students in the process of teaching professional proficiency in a foreign language is such a level of language education as a specialty that allows improving not only communication skills, but also information and technical skills [1.68].

The use of multimedia technologies in the educational process provides a wide opportunity for students to enter into live communication with a native speaker in real time and with a delay in time:

- Actively involve students in the language environment and overcome the language barrier;
- for creative activity of students;
- Improving communicative and intercultural competencies;

- motivation of students to learn a foreign language and culture. Using Internet resources in teaching foreign languages, integrating Internet tools into the educational process, allows you to more effectively solve a number of didactic tasks to form and improve reading skills, directly use;

- Network materials of varying degrees of complexity;

Modern pedagogical science seeks to use new technologies in training. Features are interactive dialogues, speech recognition systems for pronunciation visualization, animated videos that demonstrate the articulation of exercises sounds for the development of all types of speech skills, video releases with translation, and tracking of training results.

The use of multimedia technology in the learning process allows us to improve the process of organic combination of traditional forms and methods of education, innovative educational information game modeling design and analytical functions, to fulfill such a generally didactic principle of visibility, availability of feasible difficulty, systemicity, transition from training to an educated positive emotional background of learning, connection of theory with practice. Multimedia technologies act as a special intellectual means of legality and have a number of advantages over other information technologies, since they 1 Are a pedagogical means of constant improvement and methods of education in modern conditions [3.49]. They provide an opportunity to identify and support students with linguistic H abilities [2.37]. They are the basis of distance learning. We provide access to advanced methods of educating and teaching the general pedagogical community thanks to the worldwide Internet network of an extensive communication network to the pedagogical conditions of the effectiveness of using multimedia kits at a university: the feasibility of using multimedia kits: adaptation or optimal selection of multimedia programs, their fragments or combinations in accordance with the goals of the lesson, the level of training of students, compliance with methodological and hygienic rules for the use of multimedia.

It is today that the importance of the knowledge of a foreign language teacher in the use of information and communication technologies, including knowledge and skills to teach aspects of language and speech based on modern ICTs is emphasized. Thus, a combination of traditional teaching methods of language and new ones will allow for a higher level of learning [1.51].

CONCLUSION.

At present, however, the use of multimedia for the purpose of self-work in learning a foreign language is constrained by the largely high cost of computer technology, as well as the lack of a sufficient number of theoretically sound and experimentally tested computer programs intended for self-work in teaching a foreign language.

In general, at the moment there is a situation where, on the one hand, there is a small number of theoretical studies that have not been widely introduced into practice, and on the other hand, a mass of disparate programs that do not have a serious theoretical base.

LIST OF LITERATURE:

Frolova N. The problems of using multimedia technologies in high school High Technologies in the pedagogical process are the abstracts of the reports of the inter-university scientific methodological conference of university teachers, scientists and specialists - N. Novgorod. VITI, 2000.

Glazov B. I., Lovtsov D. A. Computerized textbook-basis of the new information and pedagogical technology/Pedagogy, 1995

Ignatova N.Y. Information technology in English lessons. Foreign languages at school. 2012 №2

Cite this article:

Author(s), RUSTAMOV ALIJON, (2021). "Using Methodology in Multimedia Resources in Teaching a Foreign Language", **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 1 –5. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4740066 , Issue: 5, Vol.: 3, Article: 1, Month: May, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

Published By

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International ([TWCMSI](http://www.twcmsi.com))

